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The Impact Of Tax Reform On Tax Revenue Generation In Kogi State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the impact of tax reform on tax revenue generation in Kogi State, Nigeria. The study employed annual time series data spanning from 2008 to 2021 sourced from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) of Nigeria and Kogi State Internal Revenue Service Board (KSIRSB). The various income taxes such as PAYE, RT, OT and DA were used as proxies for tax reforms and STCR was used as proxy for Kogi State Tax Revenue generation. Ordinary Least Square method was used for the data analysis alongside with Augmented Dickey fuller (ADF) Unit Root technique for stationarity test, Engle-Granger (EG) technique and Error Correction Mechanism (ECM). Other technique in the study was descriptive statistics. All the time series variables were non-stationary at levels but became stationary after first difference as ADF unit root test proved it. The Engle-Granger co-integration test shows that, long-run relationship exists between tax reform and Kogi state tax collected revenue in Nigeria. Despite the long-run equilibrium, ECM proved it that the variables in the study can also possess short-run relationship. The regression result shows that the various income taxes were statistically significant and have positive relationship with Kogi state tax collected revenue. On the whole, the study shows that tax reform in Kogi state have the tendency to promote state tax collected revenue. The study therefore, recommends among others that there should be a periodic tax reform plan for a better and efficient tax system in Kogi state since tax play a good role in contributing positively to the Kogi state tax collected revenue.

Keywords:

1. INTRODUCTION

The governments in different parts of the world are responsible for the protection life and property, provision of basic social amenities, infrastructures, among others. Similarly, the federal as well as the state governments in Nigeria also carry out these responsibilities for the citizens. To discharge their responsibilities effectively, the government needs adequate funding as a necessity to perform creditably, all things being equal. This need for finance to function effectively prompted the government at different levels to resort to tax among other sources of revenue available in the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (Olaoye, 2021). Even though it has provided in the constitution, it is further dependent on the ability of the tax administration to generate sufficient tax revenue in an efficient manner (Bird & Zolt, 2008) which in some cases, are not obtainable. That is why the contribution of Nigeria's tax to GDP is described as one of the poorest in Africa and it keeps fluctuating in a decreasing rate (Adereti, Adesina & Sanni, 2021). The figures contributed to the GDP in 2011 stood at 9.6% and dropped to 7% in 2012, then to 5.3% in 2016 and later increased slightly to 6.3% in 2018 and again declined to 6.0% in 2019. The figure in 2019, which stood at 6.0%, is significantly lower than that of Ghana and Egypt, which

stood at 16%, Morocco at 22%, and South Africa at 27%, respectively (World Bank, 2020). Notably, there are several sources of revenue at the disposal of government at all levels as provided in the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (Olaoye, 2021). The three main sources through which government generate revenue for financing expenditures are tax, non-tax and capital receipts. Of importance among the three sources is tax because the government mostly rely on tax revenue to function effectively. This is further dependent on the ability of the tax administration to generate sufficient revenue from taxation in an efficient manner (Bird & Zolt, 2008).

Tax revenue generation is still regarded as the second option in the face of oil revenue fluctuation and subsequent reduction in revenue allocation to states in Nigeria periodically. During the late 80s, 90s and democratic administration of Buhari, revenue allocation to states from the federal government was reducing and subsequently became grossly inadequate to cater for their financial needs (Kiabel & Nwokah, 2020). In spite of this, state governments in Nigeria are continuously confronted with challenges ranging from human capital development to infrastructural development. While the state governments do not have adequate funding to tackle their challenges, the allocation from the federal government is also insufficient (Oriakhi & Ahuru, 2014). Thus, in a bid to complement the effort of the federal government, the state governments resorted to internally generated revenue sources which tax is still prioritized (Nwakanna & Nnadi, 2018). State governments in Nigeria including Kogi have been involved in the endless imposition of taxes and levies in their quest for increased revenue to effectively implement their policies and programmes (Samuel & Gabriel, 2014).

As part of their policies and programmes, the Kogi state government in 1999 introduced the social service contributory levy which was purported to boost the revenue generation and promote the provision of infrastructural facilities for the people of the state (Umaru & Anyiwe, 2013). This avenue, in some cases, led to multiple taxation. The multiple taxes raised public outcry especially from the business community as it intensified tax evasion and tax avoidance which further reduced tax revenue. In response, the Nigerian government directed the joint tax board to review and harmonize tax administration in the country (Ola, 2012). In spite of this intervention by the federal government, tax payers still employed legal or illegal means of reducing their tax liabilities or not paying taxes at all which distorted tax revenue generation in Kogi state.

To generate more revenue in Kogi state, Governor Bello's administration in 2017 reformed the tax policy which included digitalization of tax collection system efficiency (Ibrahim, 2021). The reform was also a measure to solve the problem of corruption, weak tax administration, tax avoidance and tax evasion (Abdullahi, 2016) and increase tax revenue. It is believed that the reforms made it convenient for citizens to pay their taxes from their comfort zones which is in tandem with the kernels of world-class accountability and transparency. As part of this effort, online transaction was also introduced for easy processing of tax payments and vehicle registration as well as renewal of particulars through Kogi Revenue Service portal (Abdullahi, 2021). Since the tax policy was restructured, its contribution to the revenue generation of Kogi State has not been measured in concrete terms. This becomes necessary because this information will be beneficial to tax payers who are individuals and business organization as well as Board of State Internal Revenue, and the Kogi State government at large. As a result, this study sets out to investigate the impact of tax reform on tax revenue generation of Kogi State.

The paper is organised into five sections. Section one covers the introduction to the study. Section two discusses the literature review and theoretical framework which involves conceptual framework, a brief review of different theories, existing empirical studies, and establishes the research gap. Section three focuses on the methodology which describes the research design, sources of data, model specification and techniques of data analysis. The fourth section presents the data, analysis and discussion of result while the last section draws conclusion and makes policy recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Taxation is an instrument of fiscal policy employed mostly by the government to allocate resources, distribute income, balance payment and stabilize the economy (Idoko et al., 2016). It has been defined by many authors in different ways. This section describes the concept of taxation, the tax system, tax

administration and reforms in Nigeria, sources of tax in Kogi, the theoretical constructs on taxation and concludes with empirical studies related to this subject.

2.1 Concept of Taxation

Taxation has been defined as the transfer of resources from private sector to the public sector, so that government can meet its financial responsibilities (Appah & Oyandugahan, 2019). Oyedokun (2022) also viewed tax as the transfer of resources and income from the private sector to the public sector in order to achieve some of the nation's economic and social goals, maybe in the form of provision of additional government basic services particularly in education, public health, transportation, capital formation and in the provision of facilities. Ola (2001) Sees tax as a compulsory transfer or payment of money from private individuals, institutions, or groups to the government. It may be levied upon wealth, income, or in the form of a surcharge on price. Tax is defined as "a compulsory payment imposed by the government on individuals and corporate bodies in the governed area for which no direct goods or services are given in exchange for the payment made" (Bhartia, 2009). From these definitions, taxation can be described as a compulsory levy imposed by the government on the private sector (individuals and corporate bodies) to generate revenue for financing of government expenditures.

2.2 Tax System and Administration in Nigeria

Tax structure in Nigeria is tailored towards Nigerian governance hierarchy (Federal, State and Local Government). Operating a decentralized tax system, each level of government in Nigeria is independently responsible for the administration of taxes within its jurisdiction (Pml Advisory, 2021). Despite the decentralized tax system, the Nigeria arrangement is such that the federal government has under the legislative jurisdiction, almost all the juicy taxes even though states are also empowered to collect taxes (Anyanwu, 2018). Usually, the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) is responsible for the assignment and collection of taxes from corporate bodies, while the responsibility to assess and collect tax from individuals is that of the State Internal Revenue Service (SIRS) (Odusola, 2006).

. The personal income tax that is due for an individual tax payer in any year of assignment is payable to the state in which that tax payer is deemed to be resident. However, there is an exception for non-residents, resident of the FCT, officers of the foreign Service, and members of the Nigeria Army Forces whose tax are payable to the federal government (Olaniyi, 2014). Also, the local governments are by virtue of relevant statutes, allowed to charge and collect rates and levies (Oyinlola, 2012).

In Nigeria tax are administered by the organs of tax administration. These organs consist of the tax authorities, the Joint Tax Board (JTB), the Joint State Revenue Committee (JSRC) and the tax Appeal Tribunal (TAT) (Akanle, 2020). The FIRS deals with corporate bodies, residents of the FCT, non-residents, members of the Nigeria Navy, Army, Air Forces, and external affairs officers. Partnership and individuals that are residents of any state are assessed and taxed by that State's Internal Revenue Service, SIRS (Adesola, 2019). In the same vein, businesses and even individuals that are located within a local government area pay specified levies, rates, and fees to the Local Government Revenue Committee of that area. While the tax which the FIRS collect belongs to the federal government, those collected by the SBIR go to the state government, and those collected by the LGRC go to the local government (Acti & Abigail, 2014). In furtherance of the tax administration, the State Joint Revenue Committee (SJRC) was established in 1998 following the federal government's direction of 1998 budget announcement that the local government should be included in the State Board's activities (Appah & Oyadongha, 2019). Appah (2014) made it clear that the SJRC has the responsibility of implementing whatever decision the JTB comes up with as it also advises the states and local government on which tax collection method is appropriate.

2.3 Tax Reforms in Nigeria

Tax reform became imperative in Nigeria because of the nature of tax structure, which is complex, inelastic, inefficient, inequitable and unfair (Odusola, 2006). It is against this backdrop that Nigerian government decides to reform its tax system. The main objective behind the tax reform was to create an efficient tax system based on tax that are politically feasible and administratively practicable, thereby generating more revenue and at the same time reducing the tendency for economic distortions (Appah & Eze, 2013).

Alli (2009) opines that tax reform of the 90's was preceded by the inauguration of two study groups; the first study group with respect to direct tax was inaugurated on the 9th of January, 1991. The group was assigned to take a critical examination of the Nigeria's tax system since independence, evaluate the possible changes that have being made and assess the effectiveness of the system and proffer necessary recommendations. The second group was inaugurated on the 20th of April, 1991 and was assigned to assess the indirect tax regime of Nigeria. Consequently, the shift from foreign trade activities towards consumption-based tax was a major outcome of the study. To this extent, the value added tax (VAT) came into existence by decree 102 of 1993, but its implementation started January, 1994. VAT, therefore, replaced the sales tax, which has been in existence since 1956. It was a consumption-based tax imposed on both domestic and imported goods. However, several items such as foods, medical and pharmaceutical products, books, newspapers, magazines, house, rent, commercial vehicles and spare parts including services rendered by communities and people's banks were VAT free (Odusola, 2008)

In the 1994, the federal government's share of the VAT proceeds was 20 percent and state and local governments' received 50 and 30 percent respectively, and this situation was revised in the year 1995, as the share of the federal government was increased to 50 percent while state and local governments received 30 and 20 percent respectively (Ariyo & Ene, 2009). The agitation from the state governments that VAT supplanted sales tax which statutorily was revenue source within the domain of the states, and hence the revenue sharing formula should be in their favour as such triggered constant reviewing (John, 2021). Another important reform was the introductions of Decree No.20 of 1998 to stop the duplication of taxes at the state and local government levels and discourage the incidence of such multiple taxation (Bassey, 2020). To this extent, the Joint Tax Board was instructed to publish a list of various taxes at each of the government's level and the sub-national governments were prohibited from using ad-hoc tax administrators (Chigbu, Akujuobi & Appah, 2020).

The tax reform of 2004 constituted an integral part of the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies (NEEDS). Through wider consultations, nine bills were presented by the federal Executive council (FEC) to the national assembly for ratification (Abdulrazaq, 2019). These bills are the Federal Inland Revenue Service Act, 2004; Education Tax Act, 2004; Customs Excise Tariff and Consolidation Act, 2004; Personal Income Tax Act, 2004; Petroleum Profit Tax Act, 2004; Value Added Tax Act, 2004; National Sugar Development Act, 2004 and National Automotive Council Act, 2004. In addition to these major reforms, Adegbie and Fakile (2018) noted that the introduction of tax payers identification number (TIN) was part of national tax reform policy to bring cooperation between the state and federal government on tax issue. It is a nationwide electronic based system for the registration and storage of data of tax payers in Nigeria.

Remarkably, the tax reforms adopted in Kogi state are the same with those formulated by the Nigerian government as discussed above. To augment tax reform policy of the federal government, the state also implemented online electronic tax payment system that enable remote payment by taxpayers and at a convenience time. Kogi State Board of Internal Revenue, KSBIR was the body responsible for the formulation of the e-tax payment (Abenyomi & Oladeji, 2019). The Single most important index to measure the performance and the outcome of the tax reform is the improvement in revenue collection, particularly non-oil tax revenue. Revenue collection, therefore, serves as the baselines for assessing the impact of the tax reform (OkonjaIwela, 2012) as applied in this paper.

2.4 Composition of Kogi State Board of Internal Revenue Service and Strategies Adopted

Kogi State Board of Internal Revenue Service is a parastatal under the Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning charged with the responsibility to administer State Taxes and other revenue-yielding sources accrued to the state on the basis of residence as stipulated by decree No. 3 of 1993 (Federal Inland Revenue Service, 2012).

According to (Federal Inland Revenue Service, 2012).The KSBIRS is saddled with the responsibility to ensure effective assessment and optimum collection of all taxes and proper accountability to the state government, as well as impose penalties on tax defaulters. They also have the functions to appoint, promote, transfer and discipline employees of the state board services; advise the state government on tax

matters. The KSBIRS further carries out general control and management of services rendered on matters of policy but subject to provisions of the law.

For the purpose of easy tax revenue collection and voluntary compliance by the state tax payers, the State Government adopted tax reform strategies such as tax payer education and enlightenment, introduction of self-assessment, creation of new operational units, enforcement, collaborations with other ministries, department and agencies (MDAS), staff training as well as consultations (Oriakhi & Rolle, 2014). These reforms were put in place to achieve the goal of KSBIRS which is basically to increase internally generated revenue to fully fund the state budgets (Adedeji, 2016).

2.5 Kogi State Tax Revenue

Tax revenue in this context is one of the sources of funds accruable to Kogi state annually. It is the annual total amount of money that accrue from tax and collected by the KSBIRS on behalf of the state government. The Kogi State Internal Revenue Service Harmonization Bill was passed into law in 2016 and became operational in 2017. The essence of this law was for the purpose of carrying out assessments, collecting taxes and reporting taxes collected to the executive governor of the state (Haleem, 2021). The various taxes available for collection in Kogi state are discussed in the next section.

2.5.1 Pay As You Earn Tax (PAYE)

Pay As You Earn tax is a tax for individuals under paid employment. It is levied on individuals working in corporate organizations (Agenyi, 2019) and deducted from the employees' salaries and wages by an employer (Abdullahi, 2016). Employers are required by statute to deduct a certain amount from their employees' salaries, the computation of which is provided by the tax agency. The deduction of PAYE is to be remitted to the relevant tax authority through designated banks on/before day 10 of the subsequent month in the country (Aguolu, 2018). This tax rate moves from 7 to 24 percent of taxable income and the taxable income band ranges from NGN300, 000 to above NGN3.2 million in a year (Anyawu, 2015). With this annual range of pay in Nigeria, however, a low-income earner is exempted from minimum tax of PAYE and such a tax has the tendency of contributing more to Kogi state.

2.5.2 Direct Assessment Tax

Direct Assessment tax is a tax imposed on self-employed persons. Olatundun (2008) stated that Direct Assessment tax in Nigeria is a system through which self-employed persons are assessed and charged to pay tax based on their income. The self-employed include professionals (doctors, lawyers, architects, accountants, surveyors, consultants), contractors, politicians, mechanics, traders, welders, vulcanizers, farmers, carpenters, tailors, butchers, hair dressers, bricklayers, dyers, traders, artisans, musicians, comedians, athletes and all residents in a particular State who have any source of income, and others. Ali (2007) established that self-employed persons can be assessed in three ways which are self-assessment, government assessment and best of judgment assessment.

In self-assessment approach, the taxable person assesses themselves voluntarily, comes up with the tax payable, files the tax returns, and makes the payment to the State Internal Revenue Agency of their residence. However, the Revenue Authority may accept the assessment of the taxpayer if it is found to be accurate or may review the assessment upward or downward. The second technique is the government assessment described as a system where the State Internal Revenue assesses the taxpayer after the taxpayer has filed their annual tax returns for the relevant year of assessment. The Revenue Authority checks and verifies the assessment and makes review where appropriate. Notably, the last approach described as best of judgment assessment is an action against tax payers who fail to adopt any of the two methods above to pay their taxes. In this case, the State Internal Revenue Service assesses the taxpayer if they fail to file their returns within the stipulated time required by the law. The agency uses the information available to it to determine the tax payable by the taxpayer (Ali, 2007). In Nigeria, Anyafo (2017) opined that direct assessment tax is done annually and the due date for the filing of self-assessment returns is March 31st of every year. The taxpayers must compute their tax liabilities, file, and make payments concurrently by themselves before the expiration of the period.

2.5.3 Road Taxes

A road tax is a tax people must pay to legally drive a motor vehicle on public roads. Ola (2001) sees road tax as a mandatory payment on wheeled vehicles for using public roads in a country. Governments can

collect the road tax in a variety of ways such as vehicle registration fee, sold or purchase vehicle fee, road congestion fee, negative externality fee, import or export charges among other, and they use the money to fund improvements to transportation infrastructure, public safety, and related needs (McMahon, 2021). The amount of the road tax may depend on the size and value of the vehicle. People may need to pay additional road taxes and tolls to drive on specific bridges and roads because their upkeep is more expensive, and typically road taxes are also assessed on gasoline purchases (Dandago & Alabode, 2013). Road taxes is considered essential as a revenue generation for reasons of maintaining existing road infrastructure and constructing new ones; safety of human lives; control of numerous negative externalities arising from transportation such as air and noise pollution, traffic jams and accidents already mentioned under the safety argument (Martin, 2021).

Nigerian laws make it obligatory that all vehicles brought into the country or domestically manufactured must pay road tax for the statutory rights to ply the public roads within thirty days (Federal Road Safety Corps, 2018). They further stated that these approval requirements and attendant statutory payments are usually for Motor Vehicle registration, renewal of number plates and driver's license fees, road permits, roadworthiness assessment fees and other categories of related fines. The road tax administration may also provide special permits and licensing for motor vehicles, motorcycle, and tricycle value chains, including auto dealers, spare parts dealers, and mechanic workshops. Aside from uniform motor licensing fees through the instrumentality of the Joint Tax Board, other differences in statutory approval requirements vary based on the laws of individual states and the goods and passenger-carrying capacity, engine types and vehicle categories (Myles, 2012).

2.5.4 Other Taxes

Other taxes are taxes imposed on those activities that are less sensitive to government. They are taxes that are mostly collected at states or local governments. According to Goulder (2017), other taxes means all present or future stamp, court or documentary, intangible, recording, filing or similar Taxes that arise from any payment made under, from the execution, delivery, performance, enforcement or registration of, from the receipt or perfection of a security interest under, or otherwise with respect to, any Loan Document, except any such Taxes that are Other Connection Taxes imposed with respect to an assignment. In Nigeria, all states are collecting other taxes such as governor's consent fee, land registration fees, and other levies payable to those states (Sayode & Kayola, 2016). Also, Right of Occupancy fee and tenement rates are chargeable by state and local government authorities (Azubuike, 2020). All these charges are other taxes also collected by the Kogi state government.

2.6 Theoretical Review

2.6.1 Benefit Theory of Tax Reform

Nmesirionye, Jones & Onuche (2019) stated that benefit approach was initially developed by Knut Wicksell (1896) and Erik Lindahl (1919), two economists of the Stockholm School. In an explanation to this theory, they stated that taxes should be levied on individuals according to benefit conferred on them based on tax reform. This mean that, the more benefits a person derives from the activities of the state, the more such person should pay to the government through tax reform. This theory seeks to ensure that each individual's tax obligations are as far as possible based on the benefits received from the enjoyment of public services.

The application of this theory in Nigeria is such that there are various taxes (levies) that are collected in the state or local jurisdictions. Such taxes collected by various state or local government authorities are in the market, bus stands, among others. This fund is further used to develop various social facilities which results to social benefit to the society members. However, this theory has a limitation because if the state maintains a certain connection between the benefits conferred and the benefits derived, it will be against the basic principle of the tax. A tax, as known, is a compulsory contribution made to the public authorities to meet the expenses of the government and the provisions of general benefit. There is no direct quid pro quo in the case of a tax. Secondly, most of the expenditure incurred by the state is for the general benefit of its citizens. It is not possible to estimate the benefit enjoyed by a particular individual every year.

2.6.2 Socio-Political Theory of Tax Reform

Ogbonna and Appah (2012) saw the socio-political theory of tax reform as a theory that advocates for a tax reform system which is not designed to serve individuals but one that cures the ills of the society as a whole. The society is made up of individuals but is more than the sum of its individual members; consequently, the tax reform system should be directed towards the health of the society as a whole, since individuals are integral part of the broader society (Chigbu, Akujuobi & Appah, 2020). This theory is applicable to the Nigerian economy, since any higher tax collected as a result of tax reform may generate more revenue for government to cater for its citizen. Despite its applicability, the negative aspect of it is the fear of reduction in individual income that may lead to low demand.

2.6.3 Optimal Tax Reform Theory

Another dimension to the theory of tax reform is the optimal tax reform theory. Under this theory, it is required that the best way to raise revenue is through taxing goods or factors with inelastic demand or supply, and that taxation relating to distribution and externalities or market failures should concentrate on identifying the source or origin of the problem (Mankiw, Weinzierl & Yagan, 2009). Thus, for distribution, one should look for the source of inequality like land endowments or earned incomes and taxation should be concentrated on them. Regarding externalities, an attempt should be made to tax directly on the goods or activity that produces the externality (Slemrod, 2008). Employing the optimal tax reform theory, Newbery and Stern (2007) applied a formative framework to analyze the tax reform process. The optimal taxation approach according to them emphasizes the need to analyze the impact of the tax reform and evaluate both its administrative costs and its effects on social welfare. But the major problem of this approach is that it requires substantial data which are difficult to source in developing countries. In addition, optimal taxation assumes the existence of perfect administration, which does not exist in Nigeria and several other developing countries.

2.6.4 Laffer curve/Theory of Tax Reform

The Laffer curve is one of the main theoretical constructs of supply-side economics, and it is often used as to sum up the entire pro-growth world view of supply-side economics. The Laffer curve illustrates the basic idea stating that for any tax reform or changes in tax rates, there would be two effects: Effect on tax revenues which is the arithmetic effect and the economic effect (Laffer, 2004). This theory also shows the relationship between tax rates and tax revenue collected by governments. Busato and Chiarini (2009) published a Laffer curve for tax income and corporate taxation in the sector shadow economy in addition to finding a strong effect of the shadow economy to the level of taxation. Laffer curve shows that lower taxes may increase tax revenue. However, the hypothetical maximum revenue point of the Laffer curve for any given market cannot be observed directly and can only be estimated – such estimates are often controversial. Another implication of the Laffer curve is that increasing tax rates beyond a certain point as a result of tax reform may be counter-productive for raising further tax revenue.

2.6.5 Endogenous Growth Theory

This theory embraces a diverse body of theoretical and empirical work that emerged in the 1980 (Romer, 1994). This theory predicted that government expenditure and tax will have both temporary and permanent impact to economic growth (Barro, 1990). The discussion by Barro was that, tax will make market distortion and production expenditure will have an impact on the long-term growth rate. This theory helps to explain the implication of tax reform system in Nigeria that may distort market but can promote economic growth in the long-run if the spending of the tax revenue is done in the production sector. Despite this assertion, Nigeria government spends more in the service sector than real sector and Kogi state government is not an exception. Nevertheless, this theory will be adopted in this study.

2.6 Empirical Review

Oriakhi and Ahuru (2014) in their study analyzed the impact of tax reforms on tax revenue generation in Nigeria from 1981 to 2011. Using Johansen's co-integration methods and Granger causality tests, the authors found a positive and statistically significant long-run relationship between tax reforms and federally collected revenue. Specifically, they noted that reforms focusing on improving the tax system and reducing tax burdens enhanced the government's ability to generate more revenue.

Salami (2011) explored tax reforms and revenue trends in Nigeria, highlighting that tax reforms aimed at improving the tax system and reducing tax burdens enhance the government's revenue-generating capabilities. The findings suggest that well-implemented tax reforms can lead to a more efficient and effective revenue generation process.

Il Jung (2023) identified episodes of significant revenue mobilizations in Sub-Saharan Africa, drawing lessons applicable to Nigeria. It recommended implementing a combination of tax administration and policy measures, focusing on indirect taxes like VAT and excise reforms, and enhancing tax compliance through improved taxpayer segmentation and automation. The study emphasized the importance of high-level political commitment and social dialogue with key stakeholders in achieving successful tax reforms.

Okoye and Olayinka, (2021) examines the impact of electronic taxation on revenue generation in Lagos State, Nigeria, and offers an in-depth analysis of how digital tax systems, including e-filing, e-payment, and electronic tax clearance certificates (e-TCC), have influenced tax compliance and revenue outcomes. Using an ex-post facto research design and data from the Lagos State Internal Revenue Service (LIRS), the study highlights significant findings: e-payment and e-TCC issuance positively affect revenue generation, while e-filing shows limited impact. The document also discusses the evolution of tax reforms, challenges such as poor internet infrastructure and low IT literacy, and the broader implications for governance and economic development. It concludes that e-taxation improves convenience, transparency, and accountability in tax administration, recommending enhanced taxpayer education, investment in digital infrastructure, and policy adjustments to optimize the system's effectiveness. Overall, the study underscores e-taxation's potential as a transformative tool for addressing tax evasion, improving compliance, and boosting internally generated revenue in Lagos State.

Asaolu et al (2015) in their paper titled "Impact of Tax Reforms on Revenue Generation in Lagos State: A Time Series Approach," assesses the effects of tax reforms on revenue generation in Lagos State from 1999 to 2012. Using quarterly time-series data analyzed through ordinary least squares (OLS) regression, the study highlights a positive and significant relationship between tax reforms and internally generated revenue (IGR). The reforms, which included introducing electronic tax systems, taxpayer education, and administrative restructuring, led to a continuous increase in taxpayers and a noticeable revenue boost from 2006 onward. Key findings show that tax revenue constituted about 80% of IGR, with tax reforms playing a critical role in reducing Lagos State's reliance on federal allocations. The study concludes that tax reforms significantly contributed to revenue generation, enabling the state to fulfill its developmental responsibilities more effectively.

Idoko et al (2016) In his study "The Impact of Taxation on Revenue Generation in Kogi State, Nigeria" investigates the impact of taxation on revenue generation in Kogi State, employing both quantitative and qualitative methods. Cross-sectional data spanning 2004–2014 from the National Bureau of Statistics and the Board of Internal Revenue were analyzed using regression techniques, revealing a statistically significant positive relationship ($t = 1.619646$, $p < 0.05$) between taxation and revenue generation. Additionally, surveys administered to 300 and 200 employees from the Board of Internal Revenue and the Ministry of Budget and Planning, respectively, indicated that tax revenue positively affects economic development in Kogi State. However, tax evasion and avoidance were identified as significant challenges, negatively impacting revenue collection.

Ibadin and Oladipupo (2021) examined indirect taxes and economic growth in Nigeria for a period of 34 years starting from 1981 to 2014. Data collected was through secondary source (CBN bulletin) and then was analysed and tested for unit roots using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test. The study used Error Correction Model to assess the impact of VAT, PPT and CED on RGDP. Results of the study found that the VAT and PPT showed positive and significant correlation with RGDP.

Gale, Krupkin and Rueben (2020) carried out a study about the relationship between taxes and growth in Nigeria at the state level. This study used 1977 to 2011 data to measure the business activity. The variables used in the study were personal income per capita, employment- population ratio, amount of total state and local government tax revenue, statutory marginal personal income tax rate, adjusted marginal personal income tax rate and unemployment rate. The findings show inconsistent with the view that cuts in top state tax rates (income tax rates) will automatically or necessarily generate growth. The

result also shows that marginal tax rates generally have impact on employment and statistically significant, but economically small, effects on the rate of firm formation.

Wambai and Hanga (2018) examined taxation and social development in Nigeria: tackling Kano’s hidden economy. They found that the attitude of the government on taxation need to change and recommends a tax system that concentrate on establishing simplicity, predictability, and neutrality. Nwakanma and Nnamdi (2018) examined taxation and national development in Nigeria with the least square methodology and specification on the lin-log model of human development index. Their findings revealed that Petroleum Profit Tax, Company Income Tax and Excise Tax respectively exhibit a positive relationship with the level of national development, and a negative relationship between human development index and corporate tax. Worlu and Emeka (2017) examined tax revenue and economic development in Nigeria using the three stage least square estimation technique. The study found that tax revenue stimulates economic growth through infrastructural development. Olusanya, Peter and Oyebo (2017) investigated taxation as a fiscal policy instrument for income redistribution among Lagos state civil servants using spearman’s rank correlation coefficient and the study found a positive relationship between tax as a fiscal policy instrument and income redistribution.

Okafor (2012) empirically investigated the impact of tax reforms on Nigeria economic growth. The economic growth was proxied by Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and tax reform proxies by various taxes such as; personal income tax (PIT), petroleum profit tax (PPT), value added tax (VAT), Custom and exercise duty (CED) and company income tax (CIT). Secondary data and multiple linear regression model were adopted for the study. Ordinary least square method was used in the regression. The regression result showed goodness of fit and all the tax variables have positive coefficient showing tax reforms can stimulate economic growth.

Ogbonna and Appah (2012) using time series analysis and employing the scope (2007) examined the impact of tax reform on economic growth in Nigeria. Because the time series variables were non-stationary at levels, they employed the methodology of co-integration and error correction modeling. The use of augmented Dickey fuller showed that the variables were stationary after first difference. The partial stock adjustment model was used in estimating the ECM. The result showed that the changes in all the income taxes have positive coefficient. This implies that tax reforms will stimulate economic growth. The use of Granger casualty showed that all the income tax granger causes the GDP. Aderetis, Sanie and Adesina (2011) carried out a research work titled “Value- Added tax and Economic Growth of Nigeria” using GDP which was proxy for economic growth and value added tax (VAT) as independent variable. Ordinary least square technique was adopted. The model estimated a high explanatory power as the coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0.950544. This shows that about 95% substantial proportion of the variation in economic growth proxies by the GDP is accounted for by the variation of VAT revenue earnings. This lends credence to the catalytic role of tax reform to public generated revenue.

In the empirical review, several studies have been conducted by scholars in this regard to explore the impact of tax or tax reform on economic growth in Nigeria and some states and local governments. Almost none of the studies to the extent of literature search by the authors have examined the impact of tax reform on tax revenue generation in Kogi state, Nigeria from 2008 to 2021. Therefore, this study intends to fill the identified gap.

2.8 Theoretical Framework

This study anchored on the framework of endogenous growth theory. According to Okafor (2012), the framework is expressed mathematical as follows:

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1PPT + \beta_2VAT + \beta_3CED + \beta_4CIT + U \dots\dots\dots (i)$$

Where, GDP is Gross Domestic Product, PPT is petroleum profit tax, VAT is value added tax, CED is custom and exercise duty, CIT is company income tax and U is any other factor that may contribute to GDP in the absence of PPT, VAT, CED and CIT.

The framework of Okafor investigated the impact of income tax revenue on the economic growth of Nigeria by using ordinary least square (OLS) for the analysis. A simple hypothesis was formulated in the null form which states that there is no significant relationship between federally collected tax

revenue and the GDP in Nigeria. The regression result indicated a very positive and significant relationship between these two terms.

3.0 METHODS

This study used experimental research design which examined the cause and effect relationship between the independent variables (PAYE, direct assessment, road taxes and other taxes) and dependent variable (Kogi state tax revenue).

The model used in this paper was adapted from endogenous growth theory expressed by Okafor (2012) as stated in the theoretical framework. Okafor’s framework of the relationship between income tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria was stated in the equation form as follows:

$$GDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1PPT + \beta_2VAT + \beta_3CED + \beta_4CIT + U \dots\dots\dots (ii)$$

Where:

- GDP = Gross Domestic Product
- PPT = petroleum profit tax
- VAT = value added tax
- CED = Custom and exercise duty
- CIT = company income tax
- U = Error term

The above model has been modified as follow:

$$STCR = f(PAYE, DA, RT, OT) \dots\dots\dots (iii)$$

Equation (iii) can be re-specified as follow:

$$STCR = \beta_0 + \beta_1PAYE + \beta_2DA + \beta_3RT + \beta_4OT + U \dots\dots\dots (iv)$$

Where:

- STCR = State Tax Collected Revenue
- PAYE = Pay As You Earn
- DA = Direct Assessment
- RT = Road Taxes
- OT = Other Taxes
- μ = Statistical Error Term
- β_0 = Constant parameter
- $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Coefficients of the independent variables
- f = Functional Relationship

By expectation, all the various income taxes are to be positively related with the total Kogi state collected revenue, thus, ($\beta_1 - \beta_4 > 0$).

As the model is a Multiple Linear Regression Model, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method was the appropriate technique for its estimation. More so, the analysis and interpretation of the estimates were correct because of the linear relationship that exists between the variables.

The data used in this study are secondary data collected from secondary sources such as; Kogi State Internal Revenue Service Board (2021), National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) of Nigeria (2021). The data were subsequently analyzed through the use of Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method alongside with Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test for stationarity, Engle-Granger (EG) co-integration technique and Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) technique. Other techniques employed in the study include descriptive statistics and trend analysis. The data were analyzed through these techniques by running the regression of the model specified in the study. The use of OLS method for any regression, according to Koutsoyians (2001), yields parameter estimate with optimal properties such as unbiased,

minimum variance and efficient. Another reason for its adoption is that the computation procedure of OLS is fairly simple as compared with other econometric methods.

4.0 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Data analysis was done through descriptive statistics, unit root test, co-integration, error correction mechanism and ordinary least squares technique. The discussion of findings is presented in the following sections.

4.1 Kogi State Tax Revenue

The data for this research presented in table 4.1 comprised of Kogi State Tax Collected Revenue, Pay As You Earn, Direct Assessment, Road Taxes and other Taxes.

Table 4.1: Data on Kogi State Tax Collected Revenue, Pay As You Earn, Direct Assessment, Road Taxes and Other Taxes, 2008-2021

YEAR	STCR N 0,000,000	PAYE N 0,000,000	RT N 0,000,000	OT N 0,000,000	DA N 0,000,000
2008	1,209,000,000	800,000,000	109,000,000	50,000,000	250,000,000
2009	1,004,000,000	760,000,000	72,000,000	150,000,000	22,000,000
2010	1,757,000,000	1,100,000,000	75,000,000	550,000,000	32,000,000
2011	2,115,000,000	1,853,000,000	79,000,000	167,000,000	16,000,000
2012	1,974,000,000	1,351,000,000	167,000,000	418,000,000	38,000,000
2013	1,569,000,000	917,000,000	107,000,000	502,000,000	43,000,000
2014	3,377,000,000	2,560,000,000	156,000,000	621,000,000	40,000,000
2015	2,269,000,000	1,870,000,000	85,000,000	276,000,000	38,000,000
2016	3,049,000,000	¹ 1,988,000,000	19,000,000	201,000,000	9,000,000
2017	2,848,000,000	2,412,000,000	46,000,000	367,000,000	23,000,000
2018	3,185,000,000	2,806,000,000	77,000,000	298,000,000	4,000,000
2019	5,020,000,000	4,500,000,000	95,000,000	370,000,000	45,000,000
2020	6,569,000,000	5,900,000,000	180,000,000	459,000,000	30,000,000
2021	6,776,000,000	5,200,000,000	436,000,000	900,000,000	240,000,000

Source: National Bureau of Statistic (2021) / Kogi State Internal Revenue Service Board (2021)

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.2 shows the descriptive statistics for all the variables and their return series covering different sample periods. The large margins between the minimum and maximum values of all the series indicate evidence of significant variations of the trend of the series over the scope covered. In the table, the minimum and maximum values for TSCR were 2.56E+09 and 6.78E+09 which shows a large margin of 4.22E+09 indicating a significant variation of the trend in TSCR. This instance of variation of the trend in TSCR is applicable to all other variables such as PAYE, RT, OT and DA in the table. Regarding the statistical distribution of the series, all the variables prove evidence of positive skewness. But the values

for positive skewness of TSCR, PAYE, RT and DA are 1.012237, 1.906546, 2.279768 and 1.937811 not close to zero implying their non-normality distribution except for OT value 0.702694 that is close to zero indicating its normality distribution. This means the variable OT has even pattern for tax reform in Kogi state except for other macroeconomic variables that are not normally distributed which shows that the right tail is extreme. In relation to kurtosis, all the return series, TSCR, PAYE, RT and DA are leptokurtic (i.e. evidence of fatter tail than the normal distribution) as their kurtosis values are not close to 3 except for the variable, OT that shows platykurtic (i.e. evidence of lighter tail than normal distribution) as its kurtosis value, 3.286563 is approximated to 3. That is, the distribution of OT is uniform and normally distributed. The uniform distribution of OT is in line with skewness test that indicates the variable, OT has even pattern of distribution in tax collected revenue in Kogi state. This evidence was supported by the Jarque-Bera test which shows that all the series in the study are not normally distributed except the variable, OT that has its probability value 0.548797 greater than 5% (0.05) level of significance value. This implies that the macroeconomic variable, OT is normally distributed. In this case, the null hypothesis is been accepted. Therefore, the alternative inferential statistics such as student-t test, student F-test, autocorrelation test, and normality test (all incorporated in the regression models) become appropriate in this case.

Table 4.2: Descriptive Statistics and Interpretation of Results

	TSCR	PAYE	RT	OT	DA
Mean	3.05E+09	3.14E+09	1.22E+08	3.81E+08	59285714
Median	2.56E+09	2.14E+09	90000000	3.69E+08	35000000
Maximum	6.78E+09	1.20E+10	4.36E+08	9.00E+08	2.50E+08
Minimum	1.00E+09	7.60E+08	19000000	50000000	4000000.
Std. Dev.	1.85E+09	3.03E+09	1.01E+08	2.21E+08	79684405
Skewness	1.012237	1.906546	2.279768	0.702694	1.937811
Kurtosis	2.839613	6.173759	7.920157	3.286563	4.960666
Jarque-Bera	2.405795	14.35724	26.24844	1.200053	11.00438
Probability	0.300323	0.000763	0.000002	0.548797	0.004078
Sum	4.27E+10	4.40E+10	1.70E+09	5.33E+09	8.30E+08
Sum Sq. Dev.	4.44E+19	1.20E+20	1.33E+17	6.37E+17	8.25E+16
Observations	14	14	14	14	14

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 9.2, 2022.

4.2.1 Augmented Dickey-Filler Unit Root Stationarity Test

In order to ascertain the stationary state of time series variables, the researcher employs the ADF Unit Root Test as shown in table 4.3 below.

Table 4.3: Summary of Unit Root Tests

AT LEVELS				AT FIRST DIFFERENCE			
Variables	Calculated ADF	Tabulated ADF	Remarks	Variables	Calculated ADF	Tabulated ADF	Remarks
STCR	1.5708, I(0)	1% -2.7550 5% -1.0710 10%-1.6037	Non- Stationary	DSTCR	-3.29464, I(1)	1% -2.7719 5% -1.9740 10%-1.6029	Stationary
PAYE	-1.5518, I(0)	1% -2.7550 5% -1.0710 10%-1.6037	Non- Stationary	DAPYE	-5.9566, I(1)	1% -2.7719 5% -1.9740 10%-1.6029	Stationary
RT	1.1848, I(0)	1% -2.7550 5% -1.0710 10%-1.6037	Non- Stationary	DRT	-3.0593, I(1)	1% -2.7719 5%-1.9740 10%-1.6029	Stationary
OT	0.0611, I(0)	1% -2.7550 5% -1.0710 10%-1.6037	Non- Stationary	DOT	-3.9199, I(1)	1% -2.7719 5%-1.9740 10%-1.6029	Stationary
DA	-1.5655, I(0)	1% -2.7550 5% -1.0710 10%-1.6037	Non- Stationary	DDA	-4.1242, I(1)	1% -2.7719 5% -1.9740 10%-1.6029	Stationary

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 9.2, 2022

The results of the Unit Root Test using ADF even at 10% levels, shows that all time series are non-stationary at levels. This means that in absolute term, tabulated ADF values are all greater than the calculated ADF values. But these time series became stationary only after first differencing as the calculated ADF values are all greater than the tabulated ADF values even at 1% levels in absolute term. Hence, the variables have an order of integration of one. This conclusion is based on the comparison of the ADF statistic and the critical or tabulated values provided by McKinnon (1996) imply that the variables have long-run equilibrium. However, this permits the researcher to carry out the Engle-Granger Co-integration test to confirm this long-run equilibrium among available time series variables.

4.2.2 Co-integration Test

Having established the time series characteristics of the data, this study proceeds to conduct the Engle-Granger co-integration test to confirm the long-run equilibrium as demonstrated by the first difference in table 4.3. The tradition warrants that, when time series variables are non-stationary, it is important to ascertain if a long-run meaningful relationship exist among the non-stationary series. The variables are said to be co-integrated if a long-run meaningful relationship exist among the properties. The result for Engle-Granger test is given in table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Engel-Granger Co-Integration

	t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic	-2.975187	0.0221
Test critical values: 1% level	-2.754993	
5% level	-1.970978	
10% level	-1.603693	

Source: Author's Computation using EViews 9.2, 2022

The integration result based on Engle-Granger Test indicates that the variables are Co-integrated as in absolute term; the calculated ADF value, -2.975187 is greater than tabulated ADF value, -2.754993 even at 1% level as indicated in table 4.4. This means that there is a long-run relationship between the variables in the model as proved by first difference result in table 4.3.

4.2.3 Error Correction Mechanism

Table 4.5 shows the Error Correction Mechanism results. The results indicate that the coefficient of ECM is -0.068323 showing that about 6.8323% of the deviation of State Tax Collected Revenue from its short-run equilibrium is removed and therefore the relationship between the dependent variable, TSCR and the independent variables can be established not only in the long-run but also in the short-run.

The independence variables are correctly signed showing positive relationship between tax reform and State Tax Collected Revenue (STCR) of Kogi State even in the short-run. Furthermore, the coefficients of the variables are all statistically significant as all the probabilities of the variables are less than 5% level of significance. This result is consistent with that of earlier scholars (Ogbonna & Appah, 2012; Worlu & Emeka, 2017; Ibadin & Oladipupo, 2021) who found that tax contributes positively to the GDP and economic growth of the nation.

Table 4.5: Error Correction Mechanism

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
B0	2.51E+08	3.23E+08	0.778722	0.4617
D(PAYE)	5.115037	0.086657	8.327501	0.0040
D(RT)	4.145492	0.063967	7.514076	0.0030
D(OT)	3.528247	1.596889	3.030797	0.0005
D(DA)	4.307596	0.649870	5.281211	0.0167
ECM(-1)	-0.068323	0.470430	0.145235	0.0786

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 9.2, 2022

4.2.4 Regression Result (Ordinary Least Square Result)

To ascertain the long-run relationship among the variables stated in this study, OLS result was obtained as indicated in table 4.6. The coefficients of the independence variables are correctly signed showing positive relationship between tax reform and State Tax Collected Revenue (STCR) of Kogi State in the long--run. Furthermore, the coefficients of the variables are all statistically significant as all the probabilities of the variables are less than 5% level of significance. Using the 5% level of significance, individually it is proved that the coefficients of the variables; PAYE, RT, OT and DA are all statistically significant as their t-calculated (tc) values; 2.634924, 3.729013, 4.214893 and 4.834764 in table 4.6 are all greater than the value of t-tabulated ($t_t = t_{5\%(n-k)} = t_{5\%(14-5)} = t_{0.05(9)} = 1.231$). This implies that, a unit increase in PAYE, RT, OT or DA, on average TSCR increases by 2.634924, 3.729013, 4.214893 or 4.834764. This relationship is further proved by R^2 as about 71% of TSCR was explained by PAYE, RT,

OT and DA. The significance of R^2 was confirmed by the F-test, that simultaneously the independent variables; PAYE, RT, OT and DA have long-run positive impact on TSCR. The implication of these results is that Kogi state government can generate more revenue through taxes particularly in the long-run using the principles of tax reform system.

Table 4.6: Ordinary Least Square Result

Dependent Variable: TSCR				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
PAYE	0.289381	0.109825	2.634924	0.0271
RT	13.20739	4.638685	3.729013	0.0079
OT	6.581627	1.706588	4.214893	0.0046
DA	5.439351	1.516034	4.834764	0.0055
B0	6.36E+08	7.73E+08	0.823134	0.4317
R-squared	0.715603	Akaike info criterion	44.89540	
Adjusted R-squared	0.589204	Schwarz criterion	45.12363	
F-statistic	5.661473	Hannan-Quinn criter.	44.87427	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.014723	Durbin-Watson stat	1.777218	

Source: Authors' Computation using EViews 9.2, 2022

5.0 CONCLUSION

This study was set out to empirically examine the impact of tax reform on Tax Collected Revenue (STCR) of Kogi State in Nigeria. The study employed the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root stationarity test, Engle-Granger (EG) cointegration technique, Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) and Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) techniques with the annual time series data covering 2008 to 2021. The analysis started with examining stochastic characteristics of each time series by testing their stationarity using Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, Cointegration test, Error Correction Mechanism before Ordinary Least Squares method was employed. From the OLS regression results, several interesting conclusions were drawn.

To start with, all variables were integrated of order one $I(1)$ and not at level $I(0)$ while long-run relationship was established among the variables backing up by Engle-Granger cointegration technique. Despite the lack of short-run equilibrium of the variables (not stationary at level, $I(0)$), error correction mechanism was used to remove this discrepancy and as such makes the variables having both short-run and long-run relationships.

The regression result of this study shows that both individually and collectively, the tax reform proxied by PAYE, RT, OT and DA in Kogi state has long-run increase in the state tax collected revenue, TSCR. For the fact that the tax reform in Kogi state has long-run positive impact on TSCR, ECM technique proved it that the reform of this tax can also contribute positively to the state tax collected revenue even in the short-run. Therefore, tax reform system in Kogi state of Nigeria is worth to be implemented to sustain state tax collected revenue. To ensure the sustenance of tax revenue in Kogi State, an actionable plan for periodic tax reform is recommended for a better and efficient tax system. Furthermore, the government of Kogi state should do more in combating security to encourage more investment that can generate tax revenue to the state.

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